

A revision of the Mediterranean Raphitomidae 2: On the sibling species *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883) and *Raphitoma smriglioi* n. sp.

Revisión de los Raphitomidae del Mediterráneo (Conoidea) 2: las especies hermanas *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883) y *Raphitoma smriglioi* n. sp. (Gastropoda, Conoidea)

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ABSTRACT

A new raphitomid toxoglossan, *Raphitoma smriglioi* Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli n. sp., is described from the Mediterranean Sea. It is the sister species of *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883), from which it differs in the different protoconch (paucispiral v. multispiral), adding to a long list of pairs of caenogastropod species differing in their larval development.

RESUMEN

Una nueva especie de toxogloso rafitómido, *Raphitoma smriglioi* Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli n. sp., se describe del Mediterráneo. Es especie hermana de *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883), de la cual se diferencia por su protoconcha (pauciespiral vs. multispiral) y se suma a una larga lista de parejas de especies que difieren en su desarrollo larvario (planctotrófico vs. no-planctotrófico).

INTRODUCTION

The Raphitomidae are currently considered as a well supported clade of the Conoidea (BOUCHET, KANTOR, SYSOEV & PULLANDRE, 2011). The taxon Raphitomidae Bellardi 1875 is based on the genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847 which was introduced as comprising 30 fossil and Recent species (BELLARDI, 1847: 85), previously classified in various genera (such as *Pleurotoma* and *Clathurella*). Among the modern Authors, NORDSIECK (1977) listed 30 European species

plus several subspecies and varieties. In the revision of the Mediterranean Raphitomidae that we are currently carrying out, we estimated ca. 40 Mediterranean species, some of which are new.

Propaedeutic to the main revision, we have focused on several pairs of species, differing only or mostly in the size and shape of the protoconch. The specific distinction is based on the assumption that the dichotomy multispiral protoconch/planktotrophic develop-

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ment vs. paucispiral protoconch/lecithotrophic development (JABLONSKI & LUTZ, 1980) can be used in caenogastropods to recognise distinct sister species (BOUCHET, 1989; OLIVERIO, 1996a, 1996b, 1997), however, it should not be abused to create polyphyletic genera by artificially separating closely related species among different genera only based on their larval development (BOUCHET, 1990). In the genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847, we have scored at least eleven such pairs of species with different protoconchs (multispiral vs. paucispiral: Tab. 1). Nine pairs still pose intricate taxonomical problems to be solved before a thorough revision of all Mediterranean pairs can be published in a forthcoming paper. In a previous paper (PUSATERI, GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI & OLIVERIO, 2012) we have dealt with the rather obscure taxon *Raphitoma contigua* (Monterosato, 1884), of which we have selected a lectotype with multispiral protoconch to stabilize the usage of the name, and with its sister species with paucispiral protoconch, therein described as *R. spadiana* Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli, 2012. In the present work we present the

results on another pair: *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883) is supposed to be a relatively well known species, yet specimens with indistinguishable teleoconchs and different protoconchs (multispirals and paucispiral) are found throughout its putative range. Since the original type material has not been found, a neotype is here designated to stabilize the use of the name *Clathurella purpurea* var. *lineolata* B.D.D., 1883 based on a specimen with multispiral protoconch, and the species with paucispiral protoconch is described as new.

Abbreviations:

MNHN = Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris, France)
SMNH = Swedish Museum of Natural History (Stockholm, Sweden)
MCZR = Museo Civico di Zoologia di Roma (Italy)
HUJ = Hebrew University of Jerusalem (Israel)
IRSNB = Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Bruxelles
SMF = Senckenberg Museum, Frankfurt/M (Germany)

SYSTEMATICS (Citation of unpublished names is not intended for taxonomic purposes)

Family RAPHITOMIDAE Bellardi, 1875

Genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847

Type species: *Pleurotoma hystrix* Cristofori and Jan, 1832 (*nomen nudum*, validated by Bellardi, 1847 as "*Pleurotoma hystrix* Jan.") by subsequent designation (Monterosato, 1872: 54).

Raphitoma lineolata (B.D.D., 1883) (Figures 1-10, 19, 20)

Clathurella purpurea var. *lineolata* B.D.D., 1883: 92.
Raphitoma (*Philbertia*) *purpurea* var. *lineolata* B.D.D., Nordsieck, 1968: 177
Raphitoma purpurea var. *lineolata* (B.D.D.), Parenzan, 1970: 208
Raphitoma (*Philbertia*) *lineolata* (B.D.D., 1882 [sic!]), Nordsieck, 1977: 54, pl. 17, fig. 133
Raphitoma (*Philbertia*) *lineolata fuscata*, Nordsieck, 1977: 54, pl. 17, fig.
Raphitoma (*Philbertia*) *flavida* Nordsieck, 1977: 54 (partim)
Raphitoma (*Philbertia*) *corbis* sensu Nordsieck, 1977 (partim) non Michaud, 1838
Raphitoma lineolata (B.D.D., 1882 [sic!]), Bogi, Coppini & Margelli, 1980: 18 figs 9-10
Raphitoma lineolata (B.D.D., 1882 [sic!]), Rolán, 1983: 270, fig. 257
Raphitoma lineolata (B.D.D., 1883), Cecalupo & Quadri, 1996: 109
Raphitoma lineolata (B.D.D., 1883), Doneddu & Trainito, 2005: 149 (fig. 361)
Raphitoma lineolata (B.D.D., 1883), Repetto, Orlando & Arduino, 2005: 219, fig. 902
Raphitoma lineolata (B.D.D., 1883), Cossignani & Ardovini, 2011: 326-327

Type material: *Clathurella purpurea* var. *lineolata* neotype here designated, MNHN, St. Raphael (Var), France, height 7.2 mm, width: 2.9 mm. *Raphitoma (Philbertia) lineolata fuscata* Nordsieck, 1977 (SMF, not examined) *Raphitoma (Philbertia) flavida* Nordsieck, 1977 (Ibiza, 12 shells, SMF 337099/14, 14 syntypes, including 9 shells of *R. densa*, 3 shells of the *R. bicolor*-complex, 1 shell of *R. lineolata*, 1 shell of *R. cf. corbis*)

Other material examined: Unless otherwise stated, the shells originated after sorting bioclastic sands collected between 0–40 m depth. Spain - Punta de la Mona, Malaga, (coll. Bartolini, 18 shells); Marbella (coll. Gubboli, 2 shells); Estepona (coll. Rufini 1 shell); Algeciras (SMNH, lot 73168C, 1 shell); Ceuta North (MNHN, 1 shell); Ibiza (coll. Nordsieck, SMF 337090/4, 337091/3 and 337090/9 sub nomine *Philbertia corbis* 14 shells). France - St. Jean de Luz, Pyrénées-Atlantiques (MNHN, coll. H. Fischer, 1 shell); Le Brusq, Var (MNHN, 1 shell); Iles Embiez, Var (MNHN, 4 shells); Calvi, Corsica (SMNH, 52 specimens, lots 73171I, 73171M; coll. Pusateri, 2 shells). Bastia, Corsica (coll. Margelli, 1 shell; MCZR, coll. Monterosato, lot 16786, 2 shells). Croatia - Verunic (coll. Pusateri 2 shell); Veli Rat (coll. Melvill-Tomlin, NMW lot 12919, sub nomine ms. “*Philbertia subtilis*” Monterosato, 5 shells); Krk Is. (coll. Bartolini, 5 shells); unspecified locality, Croatia (coll. Delemarre, 4 shells). Italy - Riva Trigoso (Ge) -20 m, Liguria (coll. Sossu, 5 shells; coll. Repetto, 2 shells); Boccadasse (Ge) -50 m, Liguria (coll. Repetto 1 shell); Castiglioncello (Li), Tuscany (coll. Margelli, 8 shells; coll. Balena, 3 shells); Bagni Fiume (Li), Tuscany (coll. Margelli, 1 shell); Gorgona Is., Tuscany (coll. Balena, 1 shell). Giglio Is., Tuscany (coll. Balena, 1 shell); Gulf of Baratti, Tuscany (coll. Balena, 8 shells; coll. Nofroni, 1 shell); Giannutri Is., Tuscany (coll. Agamennone, 2 shells; coll. Smriglio, 3 shells); Antignano (Li), Tuscany (coll. Gori, 1 shell). Calabrone (Pi), Tuscany (coll. Bartolini, 4 shells); Montalto di Castro (Vt), Latium (coll. Occhipinti 5 shells); Capo Linaro (Rm), Latium (coll. Rufini 1 shell); Nettuno (Rm), Latium (coll. Occhipinti 1 shell). Capri Is., Campania (coll. Coen, Jerusalem, 11218 sub nomine ms. “*Philbertia purpurea mitis* M.” 1 shell). Campomarino, Apulia (coll. Di Niso, 1 shell); Porto S. Caterina (Nardò), Apulia (coll. Bini 1 shell); Otranto channel, Apulia (coll. Trono, 1 shell); Novaglie, Apulia (coll. Macri, 1 shell); Scilla, Calabria (coll. Vazzana, 11 shells). La Maddalena Is., Sardinia (coll. Rufini 3 shells); Ennio Falco cave, Portoconte, Sassari, Sardinia (coll. Oliverio, 3 shells); Stintino (Sassari), Sardinia (coll. Rufini 1 shell); Tres Nuraghes, Oristano, Sardinia (coll. Palmeri, 1 shell); S’Archittu (Oristano), Sardinia (coll. Sossu, 15 shells); Porto Istana (Olbia), Sardinia (coll. Doneddu 1 shell); Porto Alabe (Nuoro), Sardinia (coll. Spanu, 5 shells); Alghero, Sardinia (coll. Spanu, 1 shell, coll. Occhipinti, 1 shell). Palermo, Sicily (coll. Monterosato, MCZR 16678a, 1 shell; MCZR 16786, 4 shells + 2 shells sub nomine ms. “*acuminata*”; MCZR 16808, 8 shells sub nomine ms. “*subtilis*”; Carini (Palermo), Sicily (coll. Monterosato MCZR n. 16793 1 shell; MCZR n. 16808, 1 shell); Isola delle Femmine (Palermo), Sicily (coll. Palmeri, 3 shells; coll. Sercia 1 shell); Ficarazzi, Sicily (Palermo) (coll. Pusateri 12 shells); Trapani, Sicily (coll. Occhipinti 1 shell); Lo Scalone, Messina, Sicily (coll. Bartolini, 4 shells); Ustica Is. (coll. Villari 3 shells). Acitrezza, Isola Lachea, Sicily (SMNH 73197B, 9 shells juv.); Acitrezza (Catania), Sicily (SMNH 73097B, 1 shell); Cannizzaro (Catania), Sicily (coll. Rufini 3 shells); Ognina (Catania), Sicily (coll. Gemanà 1 shell). Marzamemi (Siracusa), Sicily (coll. Germanà 1 shell); Capo Passero (Siracusa), Sicily (coll. Margelli, 1 shell); Porto Palo (Siracusa), Sicily (coll. Germanà 3 shells); Pantelleria Is. (coll. Bartolini, 2 shells); Lampedusa Is. (coll. Agamennone, 1 shell); Lipari Is. (coll. Monterosato MCZR 16877, 1 shell). Malta - unspecified locality (coll. Mifsud, 5 shells). Wied Iz Zurrieg (coll. A.R. Arthur, 1 shell). Tunisia - Sfax (coll. Stadt, MNHN, 1 shell). Cyprus - off Larnaka, - 42 m (coll. Bartolini, 1 shell). Turkey - Adana (coll. Can Geyran Seashell Center, 1 shell).

Type locality: off St. Raphael (Var), France.

Distribution: We have examined materials from the northern, central and eastern Mediterranean, and from the southern Bay of Biscay in the Atlantic. It has also been recorded in the Ría de Vigo by ROLÁN MOSQUERA (1983: 270).

Description: [Neotype] Shell fusiform, height 7.2 mm, width 2.9 mm.

Protoconch multispiral of 2.7 convex whorls, height 315 μm , width 325 μm ;

protoconch I of 1.2 whorls, width 230 μm , with irregularly cancellate sculpture; protoconch II of 1.5 whorls, with subsutural axial threads and a diagonally cancellate sculpture on the lower part of the spire.

Teleoconch of 5 convex whorls, with evident suture. Axial sculpture of 19 slightly opisthocline ribs, and interspaces of the same width as the ribs.

Figures 1-8. Shells of *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883). 1-4, 8: neotype (MNHN, h: 7.2 mm), St. Raphael, France; 5: Ficarazzi (Palermo), Italy, h: 15.6 mm; 6: Termini Imerese (Palermo), Italy, h: 8.5 mm; 7: St. Raphael, France, h: 13 mm (photo courtesy A. Hoarau).
Figuras 1-8. Conchas de *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883). 1-4, 8: neotipo (MNHN, h: 7,2 mm), St. Raphael, Francia; 5: Ficarazzi (Palermo), Italy, h: 15,6 mm; 6: Termini Imerese (Palermo), Italy, h: 8,5 mm; 7: St. Raphael, Francia, h: 13 mm (foto cortesia de A. Hoarau).

Spiral sculpture on the last whorl of 18 cordlets, of which 8 above the aperture, with interspaces wider ($\times 1.5$) than the cordlets. Cancellation rectangular, with small and elongated tubercles at the intersection of axials and spirals. Tubercles on the adapical cordlets of the first whorls narrow and spinulose. Sculpture visible in transparency throughout the internal shell wall.

Anal sinus evident, corresponding to two spiral cordlets.

Columella simple, slightly sinuous anteriorly, gently angled posteriorly. Outer lip with 11 strong inner denticles;

the anteriormost, weakest, delimiting the siphonal canal and the posteriormost delimiting the anal sinus. Siphonal canal short, widely open, slightly curved.

Colour orange-tawny, with lighter cordlets and rare white tubercles. On the first teleoconch whorl two axials white. On the last whorl, the eighth abapical cordlet becoming lighter toward the peristome, with some white spots. The two axials closest to the peristome white on the central part.

Remarks: Variation in the examined material - The shell is rather slender

Figures 9, 10. Living animal of *Raphitoma lineolata* (BDD, 1883). 9: living specimen from Scilla (photo courtesy A. Vazzana); 10: sketch of a living specimen from Acitrezza, Catania (courtesy D. Scuderi).

Figuras 9, 10. Animal vivo de Raphitoma lineolata (BDD, 1883). 9: *ejemplar vivo de Scilla* (foto cortesía de A. Vazzana); 10: *dibujo de un ejemplar vivo de Acitrezza, Catania* (cortesía de D. Scuderi).

(h/d 2.45-2.84, mean 2.67 std 0.15), rarely exceeding 15 mm in length (7.5-15.9 mm, mean 10.3 mm std 2.2), and a maximum width of 4.4 mm (mean 3.8, std 0.7). It is possible that the dwarf forms attaining no more than 5 mm reported by Nordsieck (1977: 55) which we have never found, were in fact misidentified dwarf specimens of *Raphitoma contigua* (Monterosato, 1884), which we have observed (Pusateri et al., 2012). The teleoconch can reach 8 whorls, with 18-20 axials and 17-20 cordlets of which 7-9 above the aperture. Sometimes the axials of the last whorls are very weak. The subsutural ramp is missing, The two or three adapical spiral cordlets are finer than the others. Outer lip with 9-11 plicate inner denticles. The colour ranges from light to dark orange-tawny. The darker spiral interspaces are visible in transparency from the inner side of the aperture, on a background that is bluish only in fresh specimens.

R. lineolata has been frequently confused with *R. contigua*, from which it differs in the more slender outline (h/d >2.45 vs 2.2), the less robust shell, the lack of subsutural ramp, the narrower

aperture, the generally darker colour, and a white subsutural cordlet.

D. Scuderi, kindly, provided a sketch of a living specimen from Acitrezza, Catania, describing it as “almost entirely whitish, with snow-white spots, which cover all the body: the colour becomes yellow on the upper part” (Fig. 10 (D. Scuderi, in litt., xi/2004)). This description is congruent with a picture provided by A. Vazzana of a living specimen from Scilla, Calabria (Fig. 9). Templado & Llanso (1981) described the living animal of a specimen from Cabo de Palos (Murcia: found amidst *Posidonia oceanica* rhizomes) as: “animal blanco con puntinos brillantes en las zonas laterales del pie, en la parte basal de los tentáculos cefálicos y en el sifón” [white with small bright spots on the side of the foot, at the base of the cephalic tentacles and on the siphon]. The small discrepancies can fall within the geographic variation of the species or the specimens from Cabo de Palos may have been another species (e.g. we have no indication on its protoconch type).

Shells with identical teleoconchs of the *lineolata* type, but with two distinct protoconch types (multispiral vs. pau-

cispiral) are known, and we consider them as distinct species.

BUCQUOY, DAUTZENBERG & DOLLFUS (1883) described *Clathurella purpurea* var. *lineolata* as following: “*Jolie variété d’une teinte rosée ornée d’une linéole brune entre chaque cordon décurrent; ces linéoles sont très apparentes sur la face interne du labre*” This short diagnosis, could in principle be referred also to *Raphitoma contigua* or *R. spadiana*, which have a similar colour pattern. However, this would change the largely prevalent usage of the name *lineolata* by all modern Authors, and raise problems of synonymy with one of Nordiecks’s names. Actually, B.D.D.’s description would allow the identification of the *R. lineolata* pair of species by the reference to the darker interspaces,

visible throughout the aperture, albeit they did not include any comment on the apex. The type material of *Clathurella purpurea* var. *lineolata* has neither been found at the IRSNB (Bruxelles: T. Backeljau, pers. comm.), where the Dautzenberg collection is stored, nor at MNHN (Paris: V. Héros, pers. comm.), where most of the Roussillon material described by BUCQUOY ET AL. (1883) is preserved. BUCQUOY ET AL. (1883: 92) reported *Clathurella purpurea* var. *lineolata* from Paulilles (Port Vendres – Roussillon South). To stabilize the use of the name *Raphitoma lineolata* we have selected as a neotype a shell with multi-spiral protoconch, from St. Raphael (Var), which is located ca 300 km NW of Paulilles.

Raphitoma smriglioi Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli n. sp. (Figures 11-18, 21-23)

Type material: Holotype - Ognina, - 15 m, height 9.4 mm, width: 3.6 mm, MNHN. Paratypes - Ognina -15 m: A (height 9.4 mm, width: 3.9 mm, MNHN); B (height 5.9 mm, width 2.7 mm, subadult, MNHN); C, (height 4.2 mm, width 2.0 mm, coll. Smriglio). Brucoli, -20 m: D (height 8.7 mm, width 3.3 mm, coll. Pusateri).

Other material examined: Unless otherwise specified, the shells originated after sorting bioclastic sands collected between 0-40 m depth. France - St. Raphael (coll. Monterosato MCZR 16696, 3 shells); La Ciotat (coll. Monterosato MCZR 16733, 1 shell). Croatia – Unprecised locality (coll. Delemarre, 1 shell). Italy - Napoli, Campania (coll. Monterosato MCZR 16877, 1 shell); Capri Is., (coll. Monterosato MCZR 16733, 1 shell; coll. Coen HUIJ, sub nomine ms. “*Philbertia purpurea mitis* M (ms) typus, Capri!” handwritten by Coen, 1 shell). Porto Cesareo (LE), Apulia (coll. Micali, 1 shell); Marina di Ugento, Apulia (coll. Macrì, 7 shells); Scilla (Reggio Calabria), Calabria (coll. Vazzana, 1 shell). Brucoli (Siracusa), Sicily (coll. Pusateri, 1 shells + 2 shells subadult); Gulf of Carini, Sicily (coll. Palmeri, 1 shell); Ognina (Siracusa), Sicily (coll. Pusateri, 12 shells subadult); Cannizzaro (CT), Sicily (coll. Micali, 1 shell). Greece – Limnos Is. (coll. Sercia, 1 shell). Cyprus – off Larnaka, - 42 m (coll. Bartolini). Turkey – Bozcaada Is. (coll. Pusateri, 1 shell). Adana (coll. Can Geyran Seashell Center, 1 shell).

Type locality: Ognina (Siracusa), 36°58’N, 15°15’E.

Etymology: after our dear friend Carlo Smriglio, in homage to his contribution to the knowledge of the northeastern Atlantic malacofauna.

Distribution: known so far from the central and eastern Mediterranean Sea, where it is relatively uncommon.

Description: Shell fusiform, height 9.4 mm, width 3.5 mm. Protoconch paucispiral of 1.5 convex whorls, height 405 µm, width 400 µm; sculpture irregularly cancellate.

Teleoconch of 7 convex whorls, with evident suture. Axial sculpture of 18 orthocline ribs, and interspaces slightly wider than the ribs. Spiral sculpture on

the last whorl of 18 cordlets, of which 7 above the aperture, with interspaces wider (×1.8) than the cordlets. The first subsutural spiral cordlet finer than the others. Cancellation rectangular, with small and elongated tubercles at the intersection of axials and spirals. Sculpture visible in transparency throughout the internal shell wall.

Subsutural ramp absent. Anal sinus evident, corresponding to two spiral cordlets.

Figures 11-18. Shells of *Raphitoma smriglioi* n. sp. 11-15: holotype, Ognina (Siracusa), Italy (MNHN, h: 9.4 mm); 16: paratype B, Ognina (Siracusa), Italy (MNHN, h: 5.9 mm); 17, 18: paratype D, Brucoli (Siracusa), Italy (coll. Pusateri, h: 8.7 mm).

Figuras 11-18. Conchas of Raphitoma smriglioi n. sp. 11-15: holotipo, Ognina (Siracusa), Italia (MNHN, h: 9,4 mm); 16: paratipo B, Ognina (Siracusa), Italia (MNHN, h: 5,9 mm); 17, 18: paratipo D, Brucoli (Siracusa), Italia (coll. Pusateri, h: 8,7 mm).

Columella simple, sinuous anteriorly, gently angled posteriorly. Outer lip with 10 strong inner denticles; the anteriormost delimiting the siphonal canal and the posteriormost delimiting the anal sinus. Siphonal canal short, widely open.

Colour orange-tawny, with lighter cordlets and sparse white spots, and short white segments of the suprasutural cordlet.

Remarks: Variation in the examined material - The shell is slender (h/d 2.26-2.64, mean 2.49, std 0.12), 5.9-11.1 mm in

Figures 19-22. Protoconchs of *Raphitoma* spp. 19, 20: *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883), Ficazzini (Palermo), Italy; 21, 22: *Raphitoma smriglioi* n. sp. Ognina (Siracusa), Italy.
 Figures 19-22. Protoconchas de *Raphitoma* spp. 19, 20: *Raphitoma lineolata* (B.D.D., 1883), Ficazzini (Palermo), Italia; 21, 22: *Raphitoma smriglioi* n. sp. Ognina (Siracusa), Italia.

Table I. Provisional list of pairs of sibling species of the genus *Raphitoma*. (1) Nomen novum pro *R. brevis* Nordsieck, 1977, non Seguenza, 1880; (2) nomen novum pro *Clathurella cylindrica* Locard & Caziot, 1899 non Pease, 1860.

Table I. Lista provisional de parejas de especies gemelas del género *Raphitoma*. (1) Nomen novum pro *R. brevis* Nordsieck, 1977, non Seguenza, 1880; (2) nomen novum pro *Clathurella cylindrica* Locard & Caziot, 1899 non Pease, 1860.

multispiral protoconch	paucispiral protoconch
<i>R. bicolor</i> (Risso, 1826)	<i>R. farolita</i> Nordsieck, 1977
<i>R. contigua</i> Monterosato, 1884	<i>R. spadiana</i> Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli, 2012
<i>R. sp.</i> (probably undescribed)	<i>R. papillosa</i> (Pallary, 1904)
<i>R. lineolata</i> (B.D.D., 1883)	<i>R. smriglioi</i> n. sp.
<i>R. laviae</i> (Philippi, 1836)	<i>R. sp.</i> (probably undescribed)
<i>R. brunneofasciata</i> nom. nov. (1)	<i>R. syrtensis</i> Nordsieck, 1977
<i>R. radula</i> (Monterosato, 1884)	<i>R. neapolitana</i> Nordsieck, 1977
<i>R. oblonga</i> (Jeffreys, 1867)	<i>R. alleryana</i> (Sullioti, 1889)
<i>R. echinata</i> (Brocchi, 1814)	<i>R. nivea</i> (Marshall in Sykes, 1906)
<i>R. sp.</i> (probably undescribed)	<i>R. sp.</i> (probably undescribed)
<i>R. locardi</i> nom nov. (2)	<i>R. philberti</i> (Michaud, 1829)

Figures 23, 24. Shells of *Raphitoma* spp. 23: *Raphitoma smriglioi* n.sp., Cyprus, off Larnaka, -42 m, h: 7.0 mm; 24: *Raphitoma spadiana* Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli, 2012, same locality, h: 6.5 mm. *Figuras 23, 24. Conchas de Raphitoma spp.* 23: *Raphitoma smriglioi* n.sp., Chipre, frente a Larnaka, -42 m, h: 7,0 mm; 24: *Raphitoma spadiana* Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli, 2012, misma localidad, h: 6,5 mm.

length (mean 8.1 mm, std 1.7), and 2.6–4.2 mm in width (mean 3.2 mm, std 0.5). The colour ranges from orange-tawny to very light tawny.

R. smriglioi differs from *R. lineolata*, in its paucispiral protoconch, indicating a non-planktotrophic development (vs. a planktotrophic development of *R. lineolata*). *R. smriglioi* differs from *R. contigua* in its paucispiral protoconch, the more slender shell ($h/d > 2.2$, mean 2.63 vs. 2.2) and the lack of a subsutural ramp. *R. smriglioi* is also similar to *R. spadiana* (Fig.

24: the sister of *R. contigua*) in the general shell features but differs in the lack of a subsutural ramp and in the protoconch, which is slightly smaller and more slender in *smriglioi* ($405 \mu\text{m} \times 400 \mu\text{m}$ [h/d 1.06] vs. $425 \mu\text{m} \times 450 \mu\text{m}$ in *spadiana* [h/d 0.94]).

While *R. lineolata* ranges throughout the entire Mediterranean Sea and extends into the neighbouring Atlantic, the known range of *R. smriglioi* includes only the central and eastern Mediterranean Sea, where it is also less common than *R. lineolata*.

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